

Design and Implementation of Mini- School Workshop for Specific Skill Acquisition among Electrical Graduates of Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba.

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Abstract

Many electrical electronic graduates have very little practical knowledge or skill in the area of their studies. they therefore lack the confidence to practice in the world of works. Hence, after graduation they settle for jobs in which they do not derive satisfaction. The design and implementation of a mini workshop was therefore carried out to enhance electrical installation skills among electrical technology education graduates. The workshop was design to accommodate twelve students working simultaneously. Six work tables and four wiring boards were selected to be mounted at different positions within the workshop. Specialized electrical installation hand and power tools were procured for the workshop. Other workshops imperatives including fire extinguisher, safety signs, step ladder, table vice e.t.c were among other items acquired. It is recommended that experienced instructors be employed to teach the relevant skills to these groups of students by making use of the workshop.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study.

School workshop is any place in a school where instructions are given in the use of tools and machinery or where tools and machines are used for the repair, adjustment or manufacture of articles. It can also be perceived as a place where students are trained to acquire specific skill for commercial occupation. A mini School workshop therefore is a physical small building space with few tools and equipment where specific workshop activities takes place. The need for a workshop in any technical training institution in Nigeria cannot be over stressed. School workshop create an environment for hands-on learning characterized by problem solving, critical thinking, and concentration. It is an environment where connection between students and environment are built. Creativity and critical thinking can be achieved in a school workshop environment (Newsome, 2022). In spite of these benefits, most technical training institutions in Nigeria turnout graduates in different technical fields with very little knowledge in the practical area of their discipline. Puyate, (2006) corroborated that most technical institution graduates in Nigeria do not acquire the needed practical skills for them to be accepted in the world of works. Rasio, (2005) observed that graduates from technical teachers training institutions do not have the technical competence to teach or apply skills in occupational areas they studied. Okojo attributed this unfortunate scenarios to obsolete, inadequate or totally unavailable machines and equipment used for training of technical teachers and even where they are available they are not comparable to standard used in production in industries or the world of work. Consequently, graduates from these institutions pursue carrier in areas completely different from courses they studied with lesser job satisfaction. Little wonder therefore why there are acute shortages of qualified vocational and technical teachers in our technical Colleges. This scenario completely negate the goals of setting up these institutions which is to produce graduates who will be able to teach the vocational trades and all the vocational oriented subjects offered in junior secondary and technical Colleges.

1.2 Statement of Problems

Technical Vocational Education (TVE) is recognized as that aspect of education which leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills that enable its recipients to secure employment in a particular occupation. These skills cannot be acquired in a vacuum but rather in a well-established and functional

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workshop with the right tools, equipment and machines for effective implementation of the program. There is no gainsaying that most schools workshop today leaves much to be desired. Most of the equipment, tools and machines in these workshop have become obsolete. Consequently, Students goes through their program in core skill area without undertaking any practical activity. The long term implications of this scenario is that graduates of these programs are unemployable or do not have what it takes to be self-employed. Therefore, instead of an asset, they become liability to the nation at large. This project therefore is embark upon to reverse this ugly trajectory in Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba in particular.

1.3 Aim of the Project

The aim of this project is to design and develop a Mini-School workshop for teaching and learning skills in electrical installation among Electrical/Electronic technology students at Federal College of Education Technical, Asaba

1.4 Project Objectives Include:

- 1) Design a Mini-School workshop for twelve students
- 2) Apply for a room space of same size with the designed prototype.
- 3) Carryout Electrical wiring of the space applying the IEEE regulations.
- 4) Develop a simulated concrete walls where students can practice “Cracking Skill”
- 5) Procure and install basic tools and equipment required for the training

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This project falls under the category of design and construction. The design and implementation of the project was done in phases. Experts were consulted whenever there was need to do so in order to ensure compliance with engineering standards for building / equipping a workshop. Design of the workshop layout was done based on available funds. The workshop space was mapped out into sections. Conduit systems of electrical wiring was carried out on the space provided with full compliance with institute of Electrical and Electrical Engineering (IEEE) wiring regulation for workshops. Four work tables with drawer were constructed and installed according to the design layout. Three phase power supply source

with accessories was installed on a specified part of the workshop. Safety signs were displayed at strategic positions. The workshop is divided into sections as shown in figure 1.0

Figure 1.0 Proposed training sections

3.1 Workshop Design

The size of the workshop and the quantity of materials were determined based on the maximum number of students expected to carry out activity simultaneously. The workshop will accommodate twelve students working together at the same time. The plan and its dimension is as shown in figure 2

3.2 Material Description

Table 1 shows the description of materials that were used in the implementation of the workshop.

S /N	ITEM/ DESCRIPTION	DIMENSION
1	Work Table: this is a piece of furniture with flat top on which students can carry out supplementary installation activities	900 x 1800
2	Bench Vice : made of two parallel jaws for holding a work piece during hand operations	Medium size
3	Rigid ladder , a piece of tool that enables one complete task at height safely and efficiently	Medium size
4	Demonstration board , is a wooden flat board on which instructors demonstrates any electrical installation activities or task	1200 x 2400
5	Fire extinguisher, is a safety device used for putting off accidental fire that could occur in the workshop	Normal size

3.3 Design Calculations

The length and width dimension of the workshop were determined as shown. All measurement in this section were carried out in meters

Total number of students = 12

Number of work table = 6 arranged in two rows of three tables per row along workshop length

Size of work table = 0.9 x 1.8 two students per work table

Number of demonstration board = 4 mounted along the wall length.

Size of demonstration board = 1.2 x 2.4

Figure 3 shows the length and width dimensions of the workshop

3.4 Electrical Installation of Workshop

Conduit system of wiring was carried out on the workshop. Table 2 shows materials used for the installation.

S/N	Materials	Dimension/Rating	quantity
1	Socket outlet	13A and 15A	13A (4), 15A(2)
2	Ceiling rose	assorted sizes	4
3	Assorted cables : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 25mm² recline mains cable ✓ Single core PVC cables ✓ Neutral fused link ✓ 1mm² cables 	25mm ² 2.5mm ² 1.5 mm ²	1 roll 1 roll 3Pcs 1 roll
4	PVC conduit pipes Conduit Clips Saddles	20mm 20mm 20mm	2 dozen 20 Pcs 20 Pcs
5	Distribution board	Four Way	3 Pcs

3.5 Material Fixing / Positioning

Material mounting/ Positioning were carried out in stages; four demonstration boards were mounted on one of the four walls and wooden rails used to secure them firmly. Four work tables were positioned on the open floor 0.5 meters from each other and 1 meter from the wall to ensure free movement of students during practical sessions. The table vice were positioned at adjacent ends of each table. The fire extinguisher was positioned 1.5 meters above floor level accessible from any part of the workshop in case of emergency. Sand bucket was positioned close to one of the entrance. Figure 2 shows the positions of work tables on the floor space of the workshop.

Figure 2: Positions of work table on the floor of workshop

Figure 3 shows the position of the wiring board on the wall of the workshop:

DETAILS AT- Y

Figure 3: Positions of wiring Board on the Wall

PLAN (WORKSHOP)

Figure 4 : Plan view of Mini-workshop

4.4 TOOLS / EQUIPMENT

As part of basic requirement for any workshop, tools and equipment were procured .Table 2 shows these tools and equipment.

S/N	TOOLS/EQUIPMENT	QUANTITY	COST (#)
1	5m steel tape	6pcs	4,200
2	plier micro	4pcs	10,000
3	hack saw blade	5pcs	2,500
4	stared hammer	4pcs	6,000
5	Mallet hammer	1	2,500
6	Hack saw	1	1,500
7	Hose plier	2	6,000
8	Pin plier	1	4,200
9	1kg hammer	1	3,600
11	Spirit lever	2	5,000
12	Punch chisel	3	1,500
13	Allen key	4	6,000
14	Short hand glove	4	2,800
15	Long hand glove	1	800
16	Claw hammer	4	6,000
17	Stainless chisel	3	4,500
18	Multi meter	2	8,000
19	Multi meter	1	3,500
20	Stainless chisel sparker	1	2,500
21	Trimming knife	4	4,000

22	Plumbing	5	3,500
23	Chisel	1	1,200
24	Crimping tools	1	9,500
25	Pcs wire scraper	1	7,000
26	Wire scraper	1	9,000
27	Screw driver	100Pcs	30,000
28	Screw driver	100Pcs	73,000
29	Panda hammer	1	2000
30	Claw hammer	1	1300
31	Digital meter (Small)	2	4000
32	Digital meter (Big)	5	12,000
33	Side cutter	2	9600
34	Combination Pliers	6	6000
35	Stainless Chisel	6	6000
36	Voltage tester	1	5400
37	Voltage Alert	2	4000

5.0 Conclusion/Recommendation

A mini School workshop for skill acquisition in electrical installation has been designed and implemented. Worktables and Wiring boards were mounted at different positions given the required spacing to ease free movement during practical sessions. Relevant regulations were followed in the wiring of the workshop. Modern Hand and power Tools/ Equipment were procured and stored in a tool box constructed for that purpose. Three phase supply source was provided for powering three phase machine. Other workshop imperative, including ladder, fire extinguisher, sand bucket, safety signs were provided and mounted at different positions in the workshop.

It is recommended that qualified electrical instructors and other workshop staff be employed to expose relevant skills to students by making use of the workshop.

Example of an Electrical installation training workshop

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